

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

USE OF FEATURES OF THE TRANSIENT PROCESS OF THE SIGNAL OF THE TOTAL INSTANTANEOUS POWER OF THE THREE-PHASE NETWORK FOR DETERMINATION OF THE ELECTROMAGNETIC TIME CONSTANT OR POWER FACTOR OF THE ELECTRICAL SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

The features of the transient process of the signal of the total instantaneous power of three phases for quickly determining the time constant (power factor) of electrical networks are considered. The possibility of eliminating the direct input of voltage into the decision device by using a test voltage signal is shown. The structure of a microprocessor device for determining the overheating temperature of IMs during frequent starts is presented.

Keywords: transient process, instantaneous power, time constant, power factor, test power, test voltage signal.

The most important parameter of an electrical circuit is the electromagnetic time constant τ , which characterizes the rate of attenuation of the transient process in the circuit. Knowing the value $\tau=L/R$ allows you to determine the power factor of the network ($\cos\phi$) and distinguish a short circuit in the network from the inrush currents of electric motors, and changing τ allows to determine the temperature of the equipment during operation.

Since the rate of attenuation of the transient process depends on the electromagnetic time constant (τ), it can only be determined from an analysis of the transient process itself. However, the transient process of changing the phase current or instantaneous power of one phase depends not only on τ , but also on the random initial phase of the voltage ψ at the moment of disturbance in the network, which does not allow directly using these processes to determine τ .

But the character of change of the total instantaneous power of the three phases in a symmetrical three-phase system does not depend on the initial phase voltage when a disturbance occurs. In steady state, this value is constant (independent of time) and equal to $3UI\cos\phi$, where U and I are the effective values of phase voltage and current, ϕ is the phase angle of the electrical circuit, related to τ by the relation $tg\phi=\omega\tau$. In this case, the ratio of the values of any two points of this transition process will depend only on the values of τ or $\cos\phi$.

Using the total instantaneous power signal [1], [2] makes it easy to determine the required time constant τ ($\cos\phi$) from the value of two discrete values.

In article [1], the problem of blocking the operation of current protection from starting currents of electric motors is considered based on an analysis of the transient process of the total instantaneous power.

Work [2] shows the use of this method to build protection against overheating of induction motors (IM) operating in intermittent mode.

The most important feature of the total instantaneous power signal is the independence of the points of occurrence of extremes from the value of τ . Thus, the first maximum and minimum of this signal occur 5 and 15 milliseconds after the start of the transition process, respectively, and their ratio uniquely determines the value of τ or $\cos\phi$.

Despite the effectiveness of this method, one significant drawback can be noted - the need to input a voltage signal into the device, which requires installing voltage transformers in the system, solving insulation issues, and complicates both the program and, most importantly, the structure of the constructing protection systems.

A natural question arises: is it possible to do without the direct input of a voltage signal, using an artificially generated (test) voltage signal?

The signal of the total instantaneous power is formed as a result of the summation of the products of phase voltages with a random initial phase ψ by the phase currents caused by the inclusion of this real voltage. In this case, the resulting signal does not depend on the value of the random initial phase ψ .

When using a test voltage signal, its amplitude can be arbitrary, since only relative signal values are used in the future. The initial phase of the test voltage signal θ must be predetermined.

To answer the question posed above, consider the dependence of the signal of the total instantaneous power of the three phases when replacing real voltage signals with an initial phase ψ with test signals with an amplitude equal to 1 V and with an initial phase (for phase a) equal to θ .

The test total instantaneous power of the three phases is described by the following relationship:

$$p_T(t) = \sum_{k=0}^2 1 * \sin\left(\omega t + \theta + k \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) * I_m \left[\sin\left(\omega t + \psi - \varphi + k \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) - \sin\left(\psi - \varphi + k \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) e^{-t/\tau} \right], \quad (1)$$

where I_m – is the amplitude value of phase currents, k – is an index taking values 0, 1, 2 for phases a, b, c, respectively. Note that if a system with electric motors is being studied, then I_m means the amplitude value of the braked motor current in steady state.

$$p_T(t) = 1.5I_m \left[\cos(\varphi + \lambda) - \cos(\omega t + \varphi + \lambda) e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}} \right] \quad (2)$$

here $\lambda = \theta - \psi$ is the difference between the initial phases of test and real voltages.

Analysis of expression (2) shows that the character of the transient process of change $p_T(t)$ has the form of damped oscillations with frequency ω relative to the steady-state value of $1.5I_m \cos(\varphi + \lambda)$

The study of dependence (2) on the extremum in t showed that all points of occurrence of extrema t_{ex} of the function $p_T(t)$ do not depend on the values of $\cos\varphi$, that is, on τ , and are determined from the expression:

$$\omega t_{ex} + \lambda = \pi/2 + (n - 1) \pi, \quad n=1, 2, 3 \dots \quad (3)$$

where odd values of n correspond to the maximum, and even values correspond to the minimum of the test total instantaneous power.

In this case, all extreme points of the resulting test instantaneous power will shift along the time axis by an

Omitting all intermediate transformations of the sum (1), we present the final expression for the test total instantaneous power of the three phases in the transient mode - $p_T(t)$.

interval equal to $\Delta t = -\lambda/\omega$, but, as in the real process, will not depend on the value of the time constant τ . All extreme values of test power will also change. In what follows, we will be interested only in the first maximum and minimum of the test transition process.

As test voltage signals can be used a triplet of arrays of sinusoidal signals shifted by 120 degrees with any initial phase, in particular, with zero $\theta=0$ for phase a. In this case, the angle λ will be equal to $-\psi$ and all extrema will be shifted to the right by the interval $\Delta t = \psi/\omega$.

Figure 1 shows the curves of changes in the real $p(t, \tau)$ and test $p_T(t, \tau)$ total instantaneous power for two values of the time constant 0.015 s ($\cos\varphi=0.208$) and 0.03 s ($\cos\varphi = 0.105$) for the initial phase of the real voltage $\psi = 0.25 \pi$.

Fig. 1 Dependencies of actual $p=(t, \tau)$ and test $p_T=(t, \tau)$ capacities for two values τ

It can be seen that the test power curves (top) are shifted relative to the real ones to the right by 2.5 ms, which corresponds to the value $\Delta t = 0.25\pi/\omega$. Note that each increment of the initial phase of the real voltage by $\Delta\psi = 0.1\pi$ corresponds to a shift of the extrema of the test total instantaneous power to the right by 1 ms.

This means that by the position on the time axis of the extrema of the test power signal, it is possible to unambiguously determine the initial phase ψ of the real voltage signal that caused the real transient process.

Let's look at this in more detail. To do this, we determine the moment in time when the first maximum of test power occurs from (3) at $n=1$.

$$\omega t_{Tmax} = \pi/2 - \lambda = \pi/2 + \psi = 0.005\omega + \psi, \quad (4)$$

but this is the phase angle of the real voltage in phase a, which caused this transient process at the point of the first real maximum (5 ms). This means that the test voltage samples at point t_{Tmax} will be proportional to the real voltage samples at this point

$$u_T(t_{Tmax}) = \sin(\omega t_{Tmax} + k2\pi/3), \quad k=0, 1, 2. \quad (5)$$

Therefore, in order to determine the value proportional to the first maximum of the real process, it is enough to multiply the indicated samples of the test voltage signal (5) by three samples of phase currents $i_{5a,b,c}$ saved in advance during scanning at a time of 5 ms from the beginning of the disturbance and add the three resulting products

Similarly, by remembering three current samples at a time of 15 ms, multiplying them by three samples of the test signal $u_T(t_{Tmin})$ and summing the products, we will determine the first minimum of the real process.

Thus, we can formulate the following algorithm for determining the time constant τ , using a voltage test signal for a real transient process of changing phase currents.

From the moment the disturbance (start) begins, we scan the discrete array of three currents $i_{a,b,c}$ and multiply and sum this array phase by phase by the array of test voltages stored in memory $u_T(t) = \sin(\omega t + k2\pi/3)$, ($k=0, 1, 2$), thus forming the transient process of the test instantaneous power $p_T(t)$. During the scanning process, we remember 6 discrete phase currents at 5 and 15 ms from the beginning of the disturbance.

We fix the points where the first maximum and minimum test power t_{Tmax} and t_{Tmin} appear and multiply the test signal samples for these points $u_T(t_{Tmax})$ and $u_T(t_{Tmin})$ by the saved current samples $i_{5a,b,c}$ and $i_{15a,b,c}$. Summing up the resulting products, we obtain

conditional (without taking into account the actual voltage value) magnitudes of the first maximum $P_5 = P_{max}$ and the first minimum $P_{15} = P_{min}$ of the real total instantaneous power $p(t, \tau)$.

As a criterion for determining the time constant τ , you can choose the ratio P_{15}/P_5 , but, as analysis has shown, it is more advisable as a criterion for determining τ to choose not the direct ratio of extreme power values, but the ratio of their difference to their sum:

$$KR(\tau) = \frac{P_5 - P_{15}}{P_5 + P_{15}} = \frac{e^{-0.005/\tau} + e^{-0.015/\tau}}{\frac{2}{\omega\tau} + e^{-0.005/\tau} - e^{-0.015/\tau}} \quad (6)$$

The analytical relationship $KR(\tau)$ is very complex, so it is impossible to obtain an exact inverse relationship $\tau = f(KR)$. Therefore, to find the time constants of interest to us, we can use either tabular calculation values $\tau = f(KR)$ or approximation formulas.

Figure 2 shows the $KR(\tau)$ dependence calculated from (6) - solid line. It can be seen that in the range of changes from $\tau=5$ ms ($\cos\varphi=0.537$) to $\tau=20$ ms ($\cos\varphi=0.157$) this dependence is almost linear and quite accurately approximated by a straight line (dashed line):

$$aKR(\tau) = 118(\tau - 0.003), \quad (7)$$

from where it is easy to obtain an approximate inverse relationship $\tau \approx f(KR)$:

$$\tau \approx \frac{KR + 0.354}{118}. \quad (8)$$

Fig. 2 Dependences of $KR(\tau)$ and $[aKR(\tau) - 0.05]$ on values τ

Using the test power (test voltage) method allows you to eliminate the need to scan voltage from the program and save, in the case of a four-wire system, three ADCs in a microprocessor device, but most importantly, eliminate the need to use voltage transformers in the device. And the use of this method in a three-wire system allows the use of only two ADCs in a microprocessor device.

As an example of the application of the considered method, we present the results of determining the overheating temperature of IMs operating in intermittent mode, but unlike that discussed in [2], which does not require the introduction of voltage signals into the system.

Repeated short-term operating mode is the most difficult operating mode for engines in terms of over-

heating, due to the significant influence of starting currents. Therefore, the issue of overheating in this mode is always given increased attention.

To control the heating of IMs, contact methods are usually used based on the integration of thermocouples or thermistors into the stator winding, which is technologically difficult.

At the moment of start-up, the IM is a short-circuited three-phase transformer. Therefore, in the first few periods, while the engine has not yet begun to rotate, the transient process of current change in it can be considered as a transient process in a transformer. Consequently, the presented method can be applied at each subsequent engine start to determine the change in the time constant due to overheating compared to the constant at the initial start. Based on these constants, the engine overheating temperature is determined using the formula:

$$\theta_r = (\tau_1 / \tau_n - 1) / \alpha, \quad (9)$$

$\theta, ^\circ\text{C}$	80	100	120	150	180	200
τ, mC	11.16	10.49	9.9	9.12	8.5	8.065
$\theta_r, ^\circ\text{C}$	79.631	99.509	119.37	149.15	178.9	198.72

From the above results it is clear that the error in determining the overheating temperature of the IM in a wide temperature range does not exceed 1%. This shows the effectiveness of using this method to control the overheating of the IM at the time of the next start

where τ_1 - corresponds to the initial “cold” start, τ_n - calculation for each subsequent start, α – generalized temperature coefficient for a given AM.

The following remark should be made regarding the coefficient α . The presented method for determining the time constant τ gives a generalized value of this quantity, taking into account both losses in copper and losses in steel. Therefore, the temperature coefficient α is also some generalized value, close, but not equal, to the temperature coefficient of copper. It apparently should be determined experimentally for each type of engine by the manufacturer.

The table below shows the results of a comparison of the “true” (calculated based on the change in τ during heating with a coefficient α equal to the temperature coefficient of copper $4.3 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ } 1/^\circ\text{C}$) overheating temperatures of the IM θ , and the calculated θ_r determined by the described method with using the approximate formula (8), in the range of $80 - 200^\circ \text{C}$ for an engine with an initial time constant $\tau = 15 \text{ ms}$ ($\cos\phi = 0.208$).

and make a decision to continue or cancel the start. The algorithm for implementing the technique for determining the time constant and temperature of the windings of the IM is briefly summarized as follows.

Fig.3 Algorithm for determining the temperature of an IM by analyzing the power

Figure 3 shows the structure of the algorithm for implementing the method for determining the time constant and temperature of the IM windings. The above operations are presented in the form of modules.

At the moment of the next engine start, module 1 multiplies the system of currents $i_{a,b,c}(t)$ received from current sensors, by the system of test voltages $u_{Ta,b,c}(t)$, recorded in memory unit (ROM) 3. Initial phase the test voltage in phase a is selected equal to zero.

In the same module 1, from the obtained dependence of the change in time of the test power signal $p_T(t)$, the moment of time t_{Tmax} when the test power reaches the maximum value P_{Tmax} and the moment of time t_{Tmin} when it reaches the minimum value P_{Tmin} are determined.

In module 2 (RAM), during the scanning process, samples of two triplets of phase currents $i_{5a,b,c}$ and $i_{15a,b,c}$ are stored for time points of 5 and 15 ms from the moment of disturbance (start).

In module 4, triple currents $i_{5a,b,c}$ and $i_{15a,b,c}$ are multiplied by triples of test voltages $u_{Tmax} = \sin(\omega t_{Tmax} + k2\pi/3)$ and $u_{Tmin} = \sin(\omega t_{Tmin} + k2\pi/3)$, $k=0, 1, 2$ identical to the voltage system of the

real network. The resulting triplets of products are summed up, thereby obtaining values of the maximum P_5 and minimum P_{15} of the real transient process of changing the total instantaneous power.

In module 5, the ratio of extreme values of identical power $(P_5 - P_{15}) / (P_5 + P_{15})$ is determined.

In module 6, using the table dependency $\tau = f(KR)$ or using the approximation formula (8), the current value of the time constant τ_n is determined.

In module 7, the current calculated value of the temperature rise θ_r is determined using the formula $\theta_r = (\tau_1 / \tau_n - 1) / \alpha$.

The structure of the algorithm for blocking relay protection against inrush currents [1] can be implemented similarly, since the final product of the device is a quick determination of the system time constant τ or power factor $\cos\phi$, by the values of which a remote short circuit can be clearly distinguished from the inrush current of the electric motors.

Conclusion

The features of the transient process of changing the total instantaneous power of a three-phase system are considered to determine the electromagnetic time constant τ (power factor $\cos\phi$) when using a test voltage

signal, which eliminates the connection of voltage transformers to the solution device and simplifies the structure and software of the microprocessor solution device. An example of using the considered method to control the overheating temperature of induction motors operating in the repetitive-short-time mode is given, and the structure of a microprocessor device for realizing this task is given.

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